

MANAGEMENT OF POSTBURN HAND CONTRACTURE - COMPARING Z-PLASTY VS Z-PLASTY WITH SKIN GRAFT

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Abstract

A severe and deep thermal injury is usually followed by sequelae of functional limitation. Contractures are more likely to occur regardless of the initial management. The most frequently occurring functional limitation sequelae includes contracture of hands, digits, and webspace. Scar excision along with local soft tissue rearrangement and/or skin grafting is used to manage the post-burn syndactyly as well as the webspace contracture. In case of metacarpophalangeal joints, the burned claw hand is presented as extension contracture and in case of proximal interphalangeal joints, it is presented as flexion contracture. The surgical intervention to ensure the complete management of these contractures include scar tissue surgical excision and resulting soft tissue defect resurfacing along with full thickness skin graft. The study is the comparative analysis of z plasty against the z plasty with skin graft in the tension free surgical treatment of post-burn hand contracture. It includes 53 post burn hand contracture patients treated with z plasty alone and z plasty with skin graft. In both treatment conditions, the design of z plasty was 40–45-degree angle. Flap rotation was without tension and mid split thickness skin graft was used to graft them. Moreover, surgical area is examined for any sort of post-operative wound healing time, infection, scar, and necrosis. Only three cases treated with z plasty alone had some complications. The results showed that treatment with z plasty along with skin graft showed better results compared to treatment of z plasty alone. The study concludes that choice of contracture treatment depends upon degree of contracture and the available surrounding healthy tissue. Moreover, the combined treatment of z plasty with skin graft showed better results compared to z plasty alone in the study.

Introduction

Post-burn contracture is defined as the tightening of skin and soft tissues following burn injury that results in deformity and restriction of mobility. Scar tissue refers to the fibrous connective tissue that replaces normal skin after burn healing. (1). Hand contracture is the limitation of functional movement in the fingers, palm, or wrist due to

post-burn scarring. Z-plasty is a surgical procedure in which triangular skin flaps are transposed to release scar contractures and redistribute tension. (2). Skin grafting refers to the transplantation of split-thickness (STSG) or full-thickness (FTSG) skin to cover raw areas after surgical release of contracture. (3,4).

The global prevalence of burn injuries exceeds 11

million cases annually, with a higher incidence in developing countries. (5). Post-burn contractures develop in up to 30–40% of burn survivors and significantly impair daily functioning. (6). In Pakistan, hand contractures are highly prevalent due to delays in seeking specialized care, poor acute burn management, and lack of postoperative rehabilitation. (7). The burden is greater in children and young adults, leading to long-term disability and reduced quality of life. (8).

Patients who experience scar contraction after burn on hand, experience limited functionality as well as restricted motion due to “hypertrophic scar” and “flexor muscles” involvement. (8, 9). They often get surgical management after contractures development. The recovery mechanism and restoration are critical in deep burns (10). The essential and detailed insight of the underlying skin restoration principles in burn cases is important. It relies on efficient grafting at appropriate site and application of restoration procedure in right position (11). Contractures usually occur because of the surrounding skin which is severely scarred in case of severe burns (12). Usually surgery releases the contracture and initially patients are normally recommended for serial casting or splinting for treatment (13). However, difficult hand contractures can occur in spite of the proper physical therapy. Furthermore, difficulty of contracture varies as it depends on duration of scarring, functional loss, and the depth of tissue

involvement (14). Therefore, the therapeutic interventions must be tailored according to patients’

injury and subsequent contractures.

The improved quality life can be guaranteed with the good and required procedures choices as well as the decision of surgery timing along with post-surgery appropriate physiotherapy (15, 16). A diverse number of therapeutic procedures are currently used in the hospital settings to treat the hand burns and associated complications such as regional flaps, free flaps, local flaps, island flaps, z plasty, v-y plasty, and skin grafts (17). Some of the surgical interventions are complicated as they are accompanied with unfit donor site and there may be a graft failure risk as well as the recurrent scar contracture (18). Sometimes, relapsed hand scar

contracture may occur after v-y plasty and z plasty (17). However, the decision for each of the therapeutic method relies on the degree of contracture and the health of surrounding tissues. It is of prime importance to evaluate the efficacy of different treatment procedures to determine functional and aesthetic recovery of burn victims (15, 16).

In the current study, the aim is to prove that some patient requires only z plasty, whereas some requires z plasty with skin graft. It depends upon the degree of contracture and the availability of surrounding healthy tissue. The z plasty is a traditional and widely used procedure to release the scar contracture (10). It is used to break the contracture. It makes interruption to the straight-line scar contractures and realigns the scars along with less tension lines (19). It has proved to be a more economical and advantageous surgical intervention to treat post-burn hand contracture including fingers, thumb, and web-spaces (19).

Methodology

In a randomised study from Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, 93 cases of post burn contracture were investigated. From them 53 patients (91.6 cumulative percent) experienced post burn hand contracture. The critical factor was determining the severity of hand burn contracture and it was dependant on the percentage of burned area, extension loss, wideness of contracture, and surgical history of the patient.

The inclusion criteria for the study includes non-circumferential scar with up to 75% circumferential, restriction up to 30-degree flexion as well as extension in hand, and absence of the joint ossification. Contracture was older than 6 months. Age limit was 71 with range of range of 5-71 years old and gender ratio was 52.7 % for males and 47.3 % for females. The exclusion criteria include contracture less than 6 months. And the patients taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDS), presence of the joint ossification, presence of wound infections, use of high dose chemotherapeutic agents or corticosteroids, presence of associated comorbidities including systemic and metabolic disorders like diabetes, hypertension, arthritis, uremia, arterial obstruction, cardiovascular

complications, renal failure, and immune-deficiency complications.

Decision of including 53 patients with post burn hand contracture was based on selection criteria and before including them in the study, informed consent was obtained. Moreover, the study protocol was approved from the ethical committee of hospital. All the patients with post burn hand contracture were analysed clinically for the type of contracture, and restricted movement.

Patients were divided into the groups namely flexion contracture, extension contracture, and combined. Subsequently, they were treated with z plasty and z plasty with skin graft depending on the degree of contracture and the availability of surrounding healthy tissue. the surgical procedures were conducted under the presence of general anaesthesia without initial tension and patients were given “cefazolin prophylaxis” antibiotic.

The design of z plasty was based on 40-45-degree angle. An incision was done on the scar followed by release of skin flap soft tissue and deep tissue elevation along with arteries and veins preservation in the flap. Then scarotomy was made on the lateral as well as the medial hand extension in accordance with z plasty design and angle. Then 2 to 0 vicryl suture was made to repair wounds without tension preceded by flap turning. In the group that undergo z plasty with skin graft, procedure was performed to turn the flap followed by skin graft procedure without tension. Following, split thickness skin graft (STSG) and full thickness skin graft (FTSG) was performed.

Following the surgery, polyfex gauze was used to do the dressing and for 10 days splint was used to immobilise the surgical area. For 5 to 8 days dressing was changed, and patients followed the follow up check up after the surgery. Conditions of all patients were monitored closely regarding scar formation such as firmness, pigmentation or wound border elevation; wound healing time like incision border closure without secretion; contracture; bacterial culture or puss secretion indicating any infection; cyanosis and damage indicating necrosis; and limited motion.

If the metacarpophalangeal joint (MP joint) experiences extended deformities, collateral ligament was released to do an arthrolysis of the MP joint. In case of predicting collateral ligament

release of the MP joint, incision of transverse release was placed proximal to the joint level and to achieve joint access distally skin was elevated. This subsequently elevated the skin flap to cover exposed joint and allowed proximal placement of skin graft to the incision for joint access.

Furthermore, active range of motion (ROM) of the metacarpophalangeal joint (MP joint) movement was measured pre and post-surgery via the lateral goniometer. The mean active range of motion was recorded between the digits and was analysed statistically before and after the surgery.

Post-surgery follow-up

The k wires were used to achieve the post-operative immobilisation through fingernails. The immobilisation of MP joint was made in 90-degree flexion in case of extension deformities. Two weeks post-surgery, the k wires or splints were removed to initiate the physiotherapy procedure. After the skin graft was healed properly, daily active and passive hand therapy for MP joints was started to achieve active range of motion as much as possible. Proper instructions were given to the patients to allow them to do the outpatient therapy for the following 6 months. In case of increased passive range of motion as compared to active range of motion, “tenolysis” was made via proximal incision to the graft placed previously.

Results

In this randomised study, 53 patients (91.6%) out of 93 had post burn hand contracture. Patients were treated with z plasty with skin graft and z plasty alone such as z plasty (17.4%), z plasty with graft (30.4%), contracture release with STSG (92.4%), and contracture release with FTSG (98.9%) was done. There was no significant difference indicated by statistical analysis between these groups regarding the gender, age, and motion range of treated hands. Patients who were treated with z plasty alone were discharged 48 hours post-surgery after the normal recovery wound was ensured including healing time, infections, and re-contractures. Patients treated with z plasty and skin graft (contracture release with STSG and FTSG) were discharged 74 hours post- surgery as time is required to look after the skin graft. Also, it demands to train patients on

how to take care of their wound after the discharge. Comparison between patients treated with z plasty with skin graft and z plasty alone indicated that patients treated with z plasty alone

developed some complications. It shows patients treated with z plasty and skin graft showed significantly better results.

Figure 1(A) Contracture of index finger (volar surface) and little finger (volar surface), release with z plasty and (FTSG). (B) Post burn contracture of little finger (volar surface) release with z plasty. (C) Post burn contracture little finger(volar surface) release with z plasty, FTSG, and K wires. (D) Post burn contracture of index,middle,ring and little finger,contracture release with z plasty and FTSG. (E)(F) Post burn contracture little finger(dorsal) release with FTSG.

Adequate position of MP joints was achieved

without exposing bare tendons after the

adequate contracted skin release (20). Therefore, skin graft was used in most of the cases and approximately there was 95% graft take of the cases and almost 20% of the grafts were healed with secondary intentions. In the cohort of flexion deformity, 12 patients were treated with scar contracture and skin graft, 57 patients with flexion contracture were treated with contracture release and STSG, and 6 patients with contracture release and FTSG. On average, recovery period was 1 - 2/3 weeks in patients treated with z plasty and skin graft

(21). Those patients showed no infections or pressure in extension of MP joints and achieved significant motion range after 5 to 6 weeks. Regardless of the prolonged recovery time for patients treated with z plasty with skin graft, there was no significant difference when compared to patients treated with z plasty alone regarding necrosis and serious infections or complications. Therefore, in terms of recovery both groups showed approximate relative similarity.

Figure 2 (A) Post burn flexion contracture ring finger release with z plasty.

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Patients treated with z plasty alone experienced recurrence of contracture post z plasty alone. Despite minor delayed healing because of z plasty complication, full recovery was achieved. Patients who developed flap tips necrosis post z plasty were subsequently treated successfully in a conservative manner. In both treatment conditions, there was almost full range of motion in thumb as well as intact neurovascular status, and post-burn scar was also palatable and soft after 1-year follow-up. Patients treated with z plasty and skin graft experienced some discomfort at their donor site that took 2 to 3 weeks to go away. Palliative treatment care protocol was followed to reduce the discomfort and donor site got healed

without further complications at the 1-year follow-up. A few numbers of patients treated with z plasty and skin graft were not satisfied with the contracture release and skin graft as they experienced MP joint hyperextension restriction. The possible explanation for scar formation and contracture recurrence was limited or lack of skin elasticity around MP joint due to tension in flaps' tip and edge. However, scar contracture was done by increasing the scar length via z plasty and split thickness skin graft (STSG) to repair the wound without tension. Nevertheless, positive recovery as well as the recurrence depend on the severity, thickness, and width of contracture and scar.

Figure 3 (A) The post burn 1st web space contracture release with z plasty (five flap). (B)(C) The post burn 2nd web space contracture release with z plasty and FTSG.

Discussion

The hands of an individual constitute five percent of the total surface area of the body whereas its loss accounts for massive loss of full body functioning (22). The loss of hand causes a significant functional impairment even if it's a small isolated injury. Since the post recovery functioning and mobility of hands highly depends on the treatment and follow up, it very important to determine the appropriate surgical procedure for the aetiology of burned hands (22). The importance of residual functioning of hand can not be more emphasised by the fact that chronically burned hands seriously disturbs the ability of an individual to work.

The post burn hand contractures are very common, and it is a significantly occurring

problem in these procedures. The fourscore of majority of severe burns includes hand burns. Normally, it takes two weeks for 1st degree and 2nd degree burns to heal with good results (9). Contrary to superficial 2nd degree burns, other severe degree burns take morae than two weeks to recover with less aesthetic results; such as profound 2nd degree burns with partial skin thickness, 3rd degree with full skin thickness, and 4th degree including nerves, bones, joints, and tendons

(23). Normally, the scar tissue formation is used to heal these acute to severe injuries and skin grafts are used to resurface these deep burns at the time of their acute management (5, 24). This helps in minimising the reformation of contractures and accounts for early motion. Sometimes, in case of

chronic burns, the damaged structure may need to be amputated in order to restore the remaining functioning (Figure 1). The time of surgical release is still debatable. According to some, it's wise to delay secondary procedure until the scar is fully matured, whereas according to others, early release is preferred as it is not associated with the mild deformity and worst outcome (25). In the current study, early release was performed to avoid the occurrence of secondary deformity with functionally limited hand contracture.

In our study, two cases who were treated with z plasty alone experienced a small degree of flap tip necrosis. The possible explanation for the low incidence of necrosis is the improved circulation of blood as well as the tension free repair (26). The partial z plasty with ninety-degree angle is used to minimise the risk of necrosis. Moreover, the combined use of z plasty as well as the skin graft was used to cover contracture because of the morbidity of large flap donor site (27). However, the choice of treatment varies from z plasty to z plasty along with skin graft. In our study, the combination of graft techniques and skin flaps was used to minimise the problems. The common problems include long-term constraint joint extension in patients with large burnt areas with mild contracture which are treated with skin flap techniques alone; and problems of reduced skin tissue and small tissue area in patients with severe contracture.

Conclusion

The procedure of z plasty and associated modified procedures are a critical surgical intervention to treat the post-burn hand contracture. Their use produces the good outcomes including functionality as well as the aesthetic results. Else, skin grafts can be used to cover most of the defects. Strict postoperative regime of physiotherapy as well as the splinting is critical for profound outcomes. Adequate flap selection based on availability of donor area and defects is a prerequisite factor for positive outcome in patients who requires flap. Moreover, selection of proper technique to release burn contracture with respect to each patient is important. Though surgeons are aware of the tension in flaps, they perform z plasty and use vicryl sutures to repair the wound with

some tension. However, the burned tissue is deficit of normal elasticity. Therefore, it is highly likely that burned tissue potentially develops necrosis or ischemia. In that case it is recommended to flap without tension in case of mild contracture of hand. Lastly, based on the study outcomes, the use of combination therapy of z plasty and skin graft is prerequisite to optimum outcome and easier compared to z plasty alone.

Recommendations

- 1. Early Referral and Proper Burn Care**
Patients with hand burns should be referred promptly to specialized burn and reconstructive centers to minimize the risk of contracture development.
- 2. Individualized Surgical Approach**
Selection of surgical procedure should be based on the size, severity, and location of the contracture. Z-plasty should be preferred for small linear contractures with healthy surrounding skin, while Z-plasty with graft is recommended for broader or deeper scar contractures.
- 3. Strengthening Postoperative Rehabilitation**
Physiotherapy, splinting, and massage must be initiated early and continued for several months post-surgery to maintain joint mobility and reduce recurrence.
- 4. Patient and Caregiver Education**
Education about the importance of compliance with splint use, exercise, and scar management should be an integral part of treatment to ensure long-term functional improvement.
- 5. Multidisciplinary Team Approach**
Collaboration among surgeons, physiotherapists, occupational therapists, and nursing staff should be reinforced to ensure comprehensive care and rehabilitation of patients.
- 6. Improving Infrastructure and Training**
Burn care facilities should be equipped with trained personnel and resources for both acute burn management and reconstructive surgery to enhance outcomes.

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